

EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HEMORRHOIDECTOMY USING THE LONGO OPERATION AND THE LIGA SURE DEVICE

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ABSTRACT

In the article, modern medical care is provided in the treatment of epilepsy in 60 patients aged 23 to 71 years. Hemorrhoid user, socio-economic importance. Traditional and modern operative treatment of hemorrhoids. Analysis of the parameters of the operation in each method: the length of the patient's stay in the hospital, the disease and the intensity of the pain.

INTRODUCTION

Hemorrhoid is a common disease in the developed countries of the world. According to world statistics, this disease occurs in 126 out of 1000 people. This indicator is increasing more and more [1,2]. The disease occurs in 43.7% of the adult population and 40% among patients with rectal diseases. Among men and women, the disease occurs in almost the same proportion, on average at the age of 30-50. This disease reduces the quality of life and causes temporary incapacity for work [2].

4/3 of patients are treated with surgery. Despite the active implementation of minimally invasive treatment methods, the most common treatment method remains the Milligan-Morgan operation [3]. Early and late complications after hemorrhoidectomy are observed in 20-34% of cases. [3.4]. Despite the fact that new methods of treatment are actively introduced into clinical practice, the most common surgical intervention remains Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy [5]. In the United States and Europe, minimally invasive methods for the treatment of chronic hemorrhoids have recently become widespread, which is associated with early diagnosis of the disease and positive results of conservative treatment [6].

But about 30% of patients require radical hemorrhoidectomy in the late (III-IV) stages of the disease, when conservative treatment and minimally invasive methods of surgical treatment are ineffective [7]. Despite the fact that various methods of surgical treatment of hemorrhoids have been developed from the time of Hippocrates to the present, this problem has not yet been fully resolved [8].

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the results of treatment in patients who underwent hemorrhoidectomy according to Milligan Morgan and using the Liga Sure device.

Materials and methods:

A retrospective study was conducted. Patients were divided into two groups. Group 1 performed hemorrhoidectomy according to Milligan Morgan. Group 2 performed hemorrhoidectomy using the Liga Sure device. A total of 60 patients. Group 1 included 30 patients with III-IV stages of hemorrhoids. They were between 23 and 71 years old, 22 (73.3%) men and 8 (26.7%) women. The mean age was 47.8 ± 24.01 ($M \pm \sigma$).

Group 2 included 30 patients with III-IV stages of hemorrhoids. They were between 29 and 69 years old, 23 (76.7%) men and 7 (23.3%) women. Mean age was 47.0 ± 10.7 years ($M \pm \sigma$). The following parameters are analyzed: the time spent on the operation, the duration and intensity of the pain, the length of stay of the patients in the hospital.

Table 1.

Classification of groups

	Liga Sure guruh	Milligan Morgan guruh
A woman	23,3%	26,7%
Male	76,7%	73,3%
Age	29-69	23-71
Average age	$47,0 \pm 10,7$	$47,8 \pm 24,01$

Table 2.

Time spent on operation in groups

	Liga Sure group	Milligan Morgan group
Average time spent on the operation (minutes)	$16,7 \pm 7,9$	$25,7 \pm 12,6$
Average duration of inpatient treatment (days)	3 ± 1	$7 \pm 2,6$

Research results and their discussion:

Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy was used in group 1. Three hemorrhoidal nodes were removed from each patient. The average time spent on the operation was 25.7 ± 12.6 minutes ($M \pm \sigma$). The average duration of inpatient treatment of patients is 7 ± 2.6 days. Severe pain syndrome in patients was eliminated with narcotic analgesics. Long-term non-healing of the operative wound (up to 2 months) was observed in 2 patients. Group 2 patients underwent hemorrhoidectomy using the Liga Sure device. The average duration of the operation is 16.7 ± 7.9 minutes ($M \pm \sigma$). The average duration of inpatient treatment of patients is 3 ± 1 day. There was no need to use narcotic analgesics in the postoperative period. There were no postoperative complications. In patients who underwent hemorrhoidectomy using the Liga Sure device, compared to hemorrhoidectomy according to Milligan Morgan, a significant decrease in the duration and intensity of the pain syndrome after the operation was observed.

References:

1. Благодарный, Л.А. Как улучшить результаты хирургического лечения геморроя / Л.А. Благодарный, Ю.А. Шелыгин // Consilium medicum. Хирургия. – 2006. – № 1. – Т. 8. – С. 49-52.

2. Воробьев, Г.И. Геморрой / Г.И. Воробьев, Ю.А. Шелыгин, Л.А. Благодарный. – М.: Литтерра, 2010. – 200 с.
3. Воробьев Г.И. с соавт., 2010, Карпухин О.Ю., 2013.
4. Кузьмннов А.М. с соавт., 2009, Ривкин В.Л. с соавт., 2011, Brown S.R. et al., 2012, Qarabaki M.A. et al., 2014.
5. Клинические рекомендации. Колопроктология / под ред. Ю. А. Шелыгина. — М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2015. — 528 с.: ил.
6. (Федоров В.Д. с соавт. Ривкин В.Л. с соавт; Воробьев Г.И. с соавт; Щелыгин Ю.А.). Нгуен Динь Тань ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ГЕМОРОЯ П-Ш СТЕПЕНИ 14.01.17-Хирургия. 2018.
7. Khuzhamberdiev, M. A., Uzbekova, N. R., Vakhobov, B. M., Usmanova, D. N., Tashtemirova, I. M., & Kodirova, G. I. (2020). The relationship between the simpatheticadrenal system and immune disorders mediators in patients with metabolic syndrome. *International Journal of Current Research and Review*, 12(22), 91-94.
8. G. I., K. ., & I. O., O. . (2022). Daily Blood Pressure Profile and Состояние Lipid Metabolism in Patients with Unstable Angina Pectoris. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 1(11), 48-51. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/rjtds/article/view/425>
9. Kodirova, G. I., Khaidarova, N. B., Olimov, I. O., & Tashtemirova, I. M. (2022). FEATURES OF HORMONAL STATUS, COURSE AND DIAGNOSIS OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION IN WOMEN OF MIDDLE AGE. *Экономика и социум*, (10-2 (101)), 96-99.
10. Kodirova, G. I., Uktamov, N. T., Olimov, I. O., & Vakhobov, B. M. (2022). GENDER FEATURES OF THE ANTIOXIDANT SYSTEM IN CORONARY HEART DISEASE WITH DYSLIPIDEMIA. *Экономика и социум*, (10-2 (101)), 92-95.
11. Kodirova, G. I., Olimov, I. O., Uktamov, N. T., & Latipova, K. Y. (2022). RELATIONSHIP OF DAILY ARTERIAL PRESSURE PROFILE AND LIPID SPECTRUM IN PATIENTS WITH UNSTABLE ANGINA. *Экономика и социум*, (10-2 (101)), 100-103.
12. Худойбердиева, Д., Сариева, Х., Хамраева, У., & Джурабекова, А. (2013). Результаты ээг исследований у детей с гиперкинетическими синдромами. *Журнал вестник врача*, 1(1), 190-193.
13. Хамроева, У., Сариева, Х., Худойбердиева, Д., & Джурабекова, А. (2013). Клинико-невролог ический статус у детей со спинномозговыми грыжами. *Журнал вестник врача*, 1(1), 179-182.
14. Parpieva, O. R., & Ugli, O. A. D. (2019). Drugs to treat the psychological state of the patients and their methods. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1 (56)), 93-97.
15. BOTIROV, M., NORMATOVA, S. A., DABIDOV, M., & TILAVOLDIYEVA, D. (2021). DETERMINATION OF FERTILITY OF HYDROPONIC SUBSTRATES IN THE EXAMPLE OF TOMATO PLANTS. *Asian Journal of Advances in Research*, 41-45.
16. Botirov, M. T., Tilavoldiyeva, D. X., & Dabidov, M. A. (2020, October). THE CONCEPT OF SUBSTRATE IN HYDROPONICS! In *The 3rd International scientific and practical conference "The world of science and innovation" (October 14-16, 2020) Cognum Publishing House, London, United Kingdom. 2020. 637 p.* (p. 27).

17. Nazirgulomovna, S. G., & Azizjon, K. S. (2023). Biophysics is the Foundation for the Development of Scientific Thinking. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(4), 285-286.
18. Kurbanova, I., Kamalova, D., Djalolova, D., & Akhmedov, M. (2021, November). Dynamical analysis of improvement of the needle mechanism in sewing machines. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2402, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
19. Kamalova, D. (2023). YOD TANQISLIGINING TA'SIRI. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(4), 135-139.
20. Камалова, Д. А. (2019). Изменения в практике оплаты труда на производстве. *Международный научно-исследовательский журнал*, (10-2 (88)), 67-69.
21. Камалова, Д. А., & Искандарова, Ш. Т. (2013). Организация эффективных медико-санитарных мероприятий в борьбе с алкоголизмом и наркоманией. *Вестник экстренной медицины*, (3), 213-214.
22. Zafarbek Mirzaolimovich Komilov, & Qo'chqorov Oybek G'ulomovich. (2023). UBAYDULLON KANHOL – XVI ASR O'RTA SHARQ YIRIK OKULISTI . *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(15), 217-220.
23. Комилова Дилдора Алишеровна. (2023). АДАПТАЦИЯ И АДАПТАЦИОННЫЕ РЕЗЕРВЫ ОРГАНИЗМА. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(15), 221–223.
24. Kamalova, D. (2023). The value of the universal progressive model in working with mothers and children in the primary care system. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 20, 60-62.
25. Рузматова, Х. К., Камалова, Д. А., & Мухаммадова, Г. К. (2023). НАРОДНОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ РАКА ЛЕГКИХ. "GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS, 9(1).
26. Камалова, Д. (2023). РОЛЬ МИКРОФЛОРЫ КИШЕЧНОГО ТРАКТА В ИММУННОЙ ЗАЩИТЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 3(12), 205–208.